

Seedboxes were transferred to iron trays (60 × 40 × 15 cm) filled with 5 cm water 7 d after seeding (DAS). The boxes were covered with nylon net cages 20 DAS and 10 moth pairs/cage released in each cage. (A cotton swab soaked in 1% sugar solution was hung inside the cage as food for the moths.)

Moths were allowed to oviposit 3-4 d. LF damage was assessed 15 d after release of moths.

The same accessions were screened in microplots (2 × 2 m).

TNAULFR831324, 832042, 842718, 842735, and 842745 exhibited good resistance in the greenhouse and in the microplots (see table). □

Reaction of rice seedlings to LF. Coimbatore, India, 1987 wet season.

Accession	Cross	Damage rating ^a	
		Greenhouse	Microplot
TNAULFR831324	Bhavani/IR4707-106-3-2	3	3
TNAULFR832042	Bhavani/ARC10550	3	5
TNAULFR842718	Bhavani/ARC10550	3	3
TNAULFR842735	Bhavani/IR4707-106-3-2	3	5
TNAULFR842745	Bhavani/IR4707-106-3-2	3	5
Balam (donor)	—	3	5
RP2430-350-54	Rasi/Chittaraikar	5	5
RP2430-361-3	Rasi/Chittaraikar	5	5
RP2430-372-75	Rasi/Chittaraikar	5	5
ARC11281 (donor)	—	5	5
Choorapundy (donor)	—	5	5
TN1 (susceptible check)	DGWG/Tsai-Yuan-Chan	9	9
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	—	3	3

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Field incidence of and host resistance to Angoumois grain moth (AGM)

K. N. Ragumoorthy and K. Gunathilagaraj, Agricultural Entomology Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai 625104, India

We surveyed field incidence of AGM *Sitotroga cerealella* O. on rice in the field at the Agricultural College in Madurai and the Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute in Aduthurai. Seed samples of 100 g for each variety were collected in polythepe bags and adult moth emergence monitored for 6 wk.

AGM emerged from 124 of 213 samples at Madurai and from 59 of 151 samples at Aduthurai. Incidence was highest in IR and CO varieties; IR20, IR50, IR54, IR64, CO 25, CO 31, CO 37, CO 42, CO 43, CO 44, ACM11, ACM12, IET7254, ADT36, AD85003, NLR9672, Ponni, TNAU801790, TNAU831293, TNAU831520, and TNAU831521 showed field infestation in both places.

We evaluated 38 CO varieties for resistance on the basis of number of moths emerging, percentage infested grains, weight loss, and weight of adult moths; 15 were resistant.

Resistant CO 1, CO 27, and CO 32; moderately resistant CO 40; moderately susceptible CO 42; and highly

Physical and biochemical characters of rices resistant to Angoumois grain moth in India.

Variety	Husk ^a thickness (cm)	Physical characters			Biochemical factors		
		Grain hardness ^a (alkali value)	Length: breadth ratio ^b	100-grain weight ^c (g)	Silica, content ^d (%)	Total protein ^d (%)	Total amylose ^d (%)
CO 32	0.031	2	4.0	1.8	18.9	5.9	23.9
CO 21	0.037	2	3.5	2.0	19.1	9.8	28.9
CO 1	0.032	1	3.1	2.1	17.9	9.2	24.5
CO 40	0.027	4	2.0	2.3	16.8	8.2	20.7
CO 42	0.019	3	2.7	2.1	16.8	6.5	19.9
CO 43	0.017	4	2.1	1.9	15.1	6.5	19.4
CO 44	0.014	5	1.9	1.9	15.1	7.6	21.9

^aMean of 10 observations. ^bMean of 15 observations. ^cMean of 3 replications. ^dMean of 2 replications.

susceptible CO 43 and CO 44 were selected to study factors conferring resistance.

Husk thickness, grain hardness (alkali value), length-breadth ratio (grain fineness), 100-grain weight, and silica,

protein, and amylose content were analyzed. In general, resistant varieties had thick husk, low alkali value, coarse grain, higher 100-grain weight, and high silica, total protein, and total amylose content (see table). □

Excess water tolerance

Breeding for submergence tolerance

S. Mallik, C. R. Lakhe, N. K. Mitra, and B. K. Mandal, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah 712102, West Bengal, India

In eastern India, rice seedlings are likely to be submerged 30-40 d after transplanting when the monsoon breaks

in mid-Jun. We studied FR13A, FR43B, and CN540, their two hybrids, and susceptible check IR20 for submergence tolerance and recovery.

Initial height and leaf and tiller number of 10-, 30-, and 40-d-old seedlings were recorded, and seedlings were submerged in either 30 or 60 cm deep water. Survival percentage, height and leaf number were taken, and